

1 Novel transmission blocking antimalarials identified through high-throughput screen
2 of *Plasmodium berghei* Oookluc

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6 Juliana Calit¹, Jessica E. Araújo^{2,3}, Bingbing Deng⁴, Kazutoyo Miura⁴, Xiomara A.
7 Gaitán¹, Maisa da Silva Araújo², Jansen F. Medeiros^{2,3}, Carole A. Long⁴, Anton
8 Simeonov⁵, Richard T. Eastman⁵, Daniel Y. Bargieri^{1,*}

9

10 ¹Department of Parasitology, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, University of São
11 Paulo, São Paulo, SP, Brazil.

12 ²Plataforma de Produção e Infecção de Vetores da Malária – PIVEM, Laboratório de
13 Entomologia, Fundação Oswaldo Cruz-Fiocruz Rondônia, Porto Velho, Rondônia,
14 Brasil.

15 ³Programa de Pós-graduação em Biologia Experimental – Universidade Federal de
16 Rondônia/Fiocruz Rondônia, Porto Velho, RO, Brasil.

17 ⁴Laboratory of Malaria and Vector Research, National Institute of Allergy and
18 Infectious Diseases, National Institutes of Health, Rockville, MD, USA.

19 ⁵Division of Preclinical Innovation, National Center for Advancing Translational
20 Sciences, National Institutes of Health, Rockville, MD, USA.

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22

23 *Correspondence:

24 danielbargieri@usp.br

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27

28 **Abstract**

29

30 Safe and effective malaria transmission-blocking chemotherapeutics would allow a
31 community level approach to malaria control and eradication efforts, through
32 targeting the mosquito sexual stage of the parasite lifecycle. However, only a single
33 drug, primaquine, is currently approved for use in reducing transmission and drug
34 toxicity limits its widespread implementation. To address this limitation in antimalarial
35 chemotherapeutics, we used a recently developed transgenic *Plasmodium berghei*
36 line, Ookluc, to perform a series of high-throughput *in vitro* screens for compounds
37 that inhibit parasite fertilization, the initial step of parasite development within the
38 mosquito. Screens of antimalarial compounds, approved drug collections and drug-
39 like molecule libraries identified 185 compound that inhibit parasite maturation to the
40 zygote form. Seven compounds were further characterized to block gametocyte
41 activation or to be cytotoxic to formed zygotes. These were further validated in
42 mosquito membrane feeding assays using *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*. This work
43 demonstrates that high-throughput screens using the Ookluc line can identify
44 compounds active against the two most relevant human *Plasmodium*, and provide a
45 list of compounds that can be explored for the development of new antimalarials to
46 block transmission.

47

48 **Introduction**

49

50 Malaria is endemic in 85 countries, and in 2020 there were 241 million cases of
51 the disease, resulting in 627,000 deaths (1). The *Plasmodium* parasite, the causative
52 agent of malaria, is transmitted to humans through the bite of infected *Anopheles*
53 mosquitoes, which take up the circulating mature gametocyte forms of the parasite
54 when they ingest blood from an infected individual. Once ingested by a mosquito, the
55 male and female gametocytes rapidly form gametes in the mosquito midgut and
56 undergo fertilization, forming a zygote, which matures after 18-24 h into the ookinete
57 form (2). The ookinete invades the midgut epithelium to the basal lamina and
58 subsequently develops into an oocyst (2), wherein sporozoites form. After around 15
59 days, the sporozoites migrate to the salivary glands of the mosquito (3), where they
60 can then be inoculated into another individual during a subsequent mosquito blood
61 meal, thereby initiating a new infection.

62 Despite the continuous decrease in malaria incident cases and mortality between
63 2000 and 2015, progress has plateaued over the past seven years (1). Vector
64 control, through the use of insecticide and bednets has been critical for malaria
65 control programs. However, parasite transmission seems to have reached a point of
66 resilience, with only moderate response to the intensification of the available control
67 measures. To make matters worse, perpetuation of low transmission aiming at
68 elimination is fragile, and malaria cases often increase in situations of national or
69 global crisis, like in the case of the Covid-19 pandemic (4), which underpins the
70 consensus that new tools to block malaria transmission are needed.

71 The *WHO Global Technical Strategy for Malaria 2016-2030*
72 (<http://www.who.int/malaria/en/>) considers that an important addition to the toolkit for
73 malaria control will be the implementation of transmission-blocking (TB)
74 chemotherapies. Among the currently available antimalarials, primaquine is the only
75 one indicated for use specifically for TB intervention in some regions (5), and recent
76 studies support the indication of tafenoquine for TB intervention (6, 7). However,
77 primaquine and tafenoquine are contraindicated in patients with glucose-6-phosphate
78 dehydrogenase (G6PD) enzyme deficiency due to risk of hemolytic anemia (8). Thus,
79 developing new, safe and widely available TB antimalarials is critical for malaria
80 control and elimination efforts.

81 In this context, we have recently used the mouse parasite *Plasmodium berghei* to
82 develop a line that expresses a recombinant nanoluciferase (nLuc) reporter only
83 when zygotes are formed, named Ookluc (9). The engineered, nLuc-reporter
84 parasite, Ookluc, can serve to assess gamete viability, fertilization and zygote
85 maturation *in vitro*, in formats amenable to high-throughput (HT) compound
86 screening. Herein, we present the application of this assay in the identification of
87 novel TB compounds.

88

89 **Results**

90

91 *High-throughput screens*

92 To increase the capacity of screens with Ookluc, the assay was optimized for
93 1536-well plate screening. The primary screening assays in 1536-well format had an
94 average Z-score of 0.68 (range 0.41-0.86). A total of 6,631 compounds from three
95 libraries were tested: the Mechanism of Interrogation PlatE (MIPE), with 2,476 small
96 molecules with annotated mechanisms of action (10-12); the NCATS Pharmaceutical
97 Collection (NPC), with 2,816 compounds approved by either the US, EU, Canada or
98 Japan regulatory agencies (13, 14); and the novel NCATS Malaria Active
99 Compounds (NMAC), with 1,339 compounds effective against asexual stage *P.*
100 *falciparum* parasites with IC₅₀s (compound concentration that inhibited 50% of
101 normalized parasite proliferation) below 2 μM in the original primary screen. Both the
102 NPC and MIPE libraries consist of approved drugs or characterized pre-clinical
103 compounds, respectively, that primarily target eukaryotic pathways, whereas the
104 NMAC collection contains both drugs, characterized compounds and novel
105 chemotypes with asexual antimalarial activity.

106 Screening of the three libraries was performed in a quantitative high-throughput
107 manner with full concentration-responses assessed (15), 321 unique compounds
108 demonstrating high quality concentration response curves (CCv2) with IC₅₀s below 2
109 μM were identified. These along with other select compounds based on known
110 antimalarial activity or relatedness to potent conversion assay inhibitors were
111 selected for screening as a validation set (total of 346 compounds; Figure 1). The
112 compound validation set was replated from stock solution and screened in three
113 independent parasite conversion assays, as well as counter screened against the
114 nLuc reporter (for reporter interference) and HepG2 cells to assess mammalian cell

115 toxicity. From the 346 compounds, 220 compounds validated with high quality
116 concentration response curves (CCv2 -1.1, -1.2) in the conversion assay with IC₅₀s
117 below 2 μM. Of these validated potent compounds, 35 compounds demonstrated
118 some inhibition of the nLuc recombinant enzyme with activity < 10 μM (with curve
119 class values of -1.1, -1.2 or -2.2), or HepG2 cell toxicity < 10 μM (same curve class
120 valuations). Excluding these counter screened compounds, 185 selective, potent
121 compounds were identified and validated in the Ookluc *in vitro* assay with an IC₅₀
122 below 2 μM (Figure 1; screening data is presented in Supplementary Tables 1-6).
123 These compounds were also evaluated against the *P. falciparum* Dd2 asexual stage
124 to assess stage specific or multistage activities, 37 of the compounds were >10-fold
125 more potent in the conversion assay with the transgenic *P. berghei*, and 39 were
126 >10-fold more potent against the asexual stages of *P. falciparum* Dd2 parasites, with
127 the remaining 111 compounds in between (Supplemental Table S7). Importantly, the
128 higher potency of some compounds in the conversion assay is due to resistance of
129 *P. falciparum* Dd2, for example the case of pyrimethamine. In other cases, the
130 comparison may point to differences in metabolic pathways. From the validated
131 compounds, seven were selected for further studies (Table 1, Supplementary Figure
132 1). These were prioritized to evaluate compounds with varied efficacy against the
133 asexual stage, in addition to the Ookluc activity, and diverse suspected mode of
134 action.

135

136 *Characterization of TB activity*

137 The seven compounds were initially screened in exflagellation assays to evaluate
138 their ability to block *P. berghei* fertilization (Figure 2A). DDD107498, faspaplysin,
139 hesperadin and nanchangmycin blocked the formation of exflagellation centers by
140 activated gametocytes, indicating that they impede fertilization by inhibiting male
141 gamete formation. In contrast, pyronaridine, batimastat and quinacrine reduced but
142 did not abolish the formation of exflagellation centers (Figure 2A), while their ability to
143 block ookinete formation was confirmed (Figure 2B), showing that they may either
144 have activity against female gametocytes (not assessed) or downstream gametocyte
145 activation, against gamete fertilization or zygote maturation.

146 The formation of zygotes in the presence of pyronaridine, batimastat and
147 quinacrine was tested 1 or 6 hrs after gametocyte to gamete conversion (Figure 3A
148 and B). Normal numbers of zygotes were observed in assays treated with

149 pyronaridine 1 hr post activation, while the number of zygotes were drastically
150 reduced in assays treated with batimastat and abolished with quinacrine (Figure 3A),
151 suggesting that pyronaridine has minimal activity against gametocytes and gametes,
152 while it remains possible that batimastat and quinacrine block zygote formation
153 through inhibition of female gametocytes/gametes. After 6 hrs, zygotes were absent
154 in all conversion assays (Figure 3B), an indication that pyronaridine blocks ookinete
155 formation through a cytotoxic effect on zygotes.

156

157 *P. falciparum* SMFA and *P. vivax* DMFA

158 To test whether compounds identified through Ookluc HT screening have,
159 indeed, transmission blocking activity, the seven selected compounds were tested in
160 mosquito membrane feeding assays with *P. falciparum* or *P. vivax*.

161 Screening the human parasite, *P. falciparum*, in the standard membrane feeding
162 assays (SMFA), only batimastat and quinacrine failed to demonstrate TB activity
163 (Tables 2 and S8). Highlighting the predictive screening potential of the Ookluc
164 reporter line in identifying compounds with TB activity against human *Plasmodium*
165 parasites. Hesperadin showed strong inhibitory activity in concentrations as low as
166 80 nM (Table 2). In *P. vivax* direct membrane feeding assays (DMFA), batimastat,
167 pyronaridine, fasicaplysin, and quinacrine did not exhibit significant TB activity, while
168 hesperadin, DDD107498 and nanchangmycin showed strong inhibitory activities,
169 comparable to those observed in the *P. falciparum* SMFA (Tables 3 and S9).

170 The *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* MFA were made adding the compounds to the
171 infected blood only 2 min before mosquito feeding, so any measured effect can be
172 attributed exclusively to compound activity against the mosquito stages. Because
173 400 nM pyronaridine added 2 min before feeding reduced 51.9% *P. falciparum*
174 oocyst formation, and because pyronaridine is a licensed and implemented
175 antimalarial, it was also tested at lower concentrations that reflected plasma levels
176 after dosing (16), in *P. falciparum* SMFA adding the drug 24 or 48h before feeding.
177 While 50 nM pyronaridine did not inhibit oocyst formation, incubating the
178 gametocytes for 48 h with 400 nM of drug demonstrated comparable oocyst inhibition
179 of 66.7% (Tables 4 and S8) as to the no preincubation at the same 400 nM (51.9%
180 inhibition, Table 2).

181

182 **Discussion**

183 In this study, we applied the *P. berghei* line Ookluc (9), a luciferase reporter line,
184 for HT screening of compound libraries in 1536-well plate format. The HT assay was
185 used to evaluate 6,631 compounds against fertilization, identifying 185 compounds
186 with TB potential. Many identified compounds have predicted mode of action related
187 to DNA replication and tubulin polymerization/depolymerization, likely inhibiting the
188 three mitotic events for male gametogenesis. Some potent compounds identified in
189 our screen have previously been identified with gametocytocidal activity, like Torin-2,
190 which was recently shown to target *P. falciparum* Phosphatidylinositol 4-Kinase (17,
191 18). Seven compounds were selected for further evaluation and were tested in
192 mosquito infections with *P. falciparum* or *P. vivax*.

193 Recent HT screens to identify TB compounds, including those with dual-stage
194 activity targeting both asexual and TB stages have been performed (18-20), yielding
195 highly potent hits. However, in our methodology, compounds were added
196 immediately prior to gametocyte activation *in vitro* or in mosquito feeding assays,
197 limiting the drug exposure of the gametocyte forms and thus focusing the assay
198 against the early parasite sexual stages that are formed in the mosquito midgut. This
199 narrow stage of the malaria lifecycle was chosen as it involves profound changes in
200 metabolic activity that may be specifically targeted by chemotherapeutics (21). Our
201 previous work demonstrated that compound activity against asexual stages or
202 gametocytes does not predict activity against parasite early stages in the mosquito
203 (9). Therefore, we screened 3 different compound collections, NMAC to identify
204 molecules with dual-stage activity, and NPC and MIPE to identify molecules with
205 antimalarial activity, yet possibly not active against asexual stages or gametocytes.

206 The 185 compounds identified with strong activity against *Plasmodium*
207 fertilization have different putative mode of actions, reflecting the abundance of
208 metabolic pathways activated in this step of the parasite life cycle. However, it is
209 notable that compounds targeting cell replication pathways are prominent, likely due
210 to the necessity of three mitotic events for the formation of the male microgametes
211 (2). Of the 185 validated compounds, seven were chosen for further evaluation
212 based on their activity against asexual stages, putative mode of action and history of
213 use as antimalarials. Of those, only two of the seven, batimastat and quinacrine, had
214 no significant activity against mosquito infections either with *P. falciparum* or *P. vivax*,
215 highlighting the predictive power of *P. berghei* Ookluc in identifying TB compounds.
216 Interestingly, the most active compounds against mosquito infection also have strong

217 activity against exflagellation, confirming previous conclusions that early steps in
218 *Plasmodium* gametogenesis are potentially effective drug targets (22), and
219 suggesting that the development of a high-throughput screening tool with an
220 exflagellation reporter may be an attractive future approach.

221 Efforts to find new medicines for malaria control can be guided by Target
222 Candidate Profiles (TCPs), dividing types of compounds according to their activity
223 against the parasite (22). One important TCP aims at targeting the sexual stages,
224 with a goal of 90% transmission blocking activity to mosquitoes seven days after oral
225 dosage, which is the mean circulation time of mature gametocytes, and half the
226 duration of gametocyte carriage after treatment with artemisinins (22). Therefore,
227 new TB compounds with intrinsic long half-life, or chemically developed for long half-
228 life, may be proposed as a component of future ACT to prevent parasite transmission
229 to mosquito after clearance of asexual stages. Moreover, they may be used in the
230 development of new antimalarials for mass drug administration for reducing malaria
231 transmission in specific epidemiological settings. Another potential use is in baits or
232 nets to render the mosquitoes refractory to infection, as demonstrated for
233 atovaquone (23).

234 Hesperadin was the most active compound against mosquito infections, with
235 strong inhibition of *P. falciparum* oocyst formation at nanomolar concentrations.
236 Hesperadin is a putative inhibitor of human Aurora kinases. In human cells, Aurora
237 kinases are important in cellular division, controlling chromatid segregation (24).
238 *Plasmodium* parasites express three Aurora kinases (25), with only modest identity
239 (~40%) to the human genes in the kinase domains. Hesperadin blocks nuclear
240 division in *P. falciparum* (26), an effect that supports Aurora kinases as the putative
241 target in the parasite. Among the 185 validated potential TB compounds, at least
242 other 3 putative Aurora kinase inhibitors were identified, in addition to hesperadin.
243 These results support further evaluation of Aurora kinases as a potential TB
244 antimalarial drug target.

245 DDD107498 is a *P. falciparum* elongation factor 2 inhibitor with activity against
246 multiple stages of the parasite (27). It is currently in clinical development with the
247 name M5717. The TB activity of DDD107498 against *P. falciparum* confirmed
248 previous results (27, 28), and our results in *P. vivax* infections of *An. darlingi*
249 mosquitoes showed comparable TB activities, highlighting the potential use of
250 DDD107498 to reduce malaria transmission.

251 Pyronaridine, a benzonaphthyridine derivative, has potent activity against
252 *Plasmodium* asexual stages targeting hemozoin formation in the parasite (29).
253 Pyronaridine has a long elimination half-life, of up to 13 days in malaria patients (30),
254 and is an approved antimalarial given in combination with artesunate, under the
255 brand name Pyramax® (180 mg pyronaridine and 60 mg artesunate). Previous
256 studies assessed the TB potential of pyronaridine and found low activity in
257 gametocyte viability or gametogenesis assays (31-33). At least one study evaluated
258 pyronaridine in *P. falciparum* SMFA, pre-incubating the gametocytes with 1 µM of the
259 drug for 24 h, and found 80% oocyst reduction (34), comparable with the results we
260 observed by adding the drug immediately prior to mosquito feeding. We also
261 demonstrate that pyronaridine is not active against *P. berghei* male gametogenesis,
262 in line with previous findings that it is poorly active against mature stage V *P.*
263 *falciparum* gametocytes (34), and we show that it likely inhibits parasite transmission
264 to mosquitoes by targeting the zygotes formed in the mosquito midgut. Whether the
265 inhibitory mechanism in zygotes is also through targeting haem metabolism remains
266 uncertain, but the fact that pyronaridine was inactive against *P. vivax* transmission
267 suggest that the target on *P. falciparum* sexual stages may be different from the
268 inhibitory mechanism described for asexual stages, since in this case the drug is
269 active against both parasite species. In Pyramax® treated patients, pyronaridine has
270 a long half-life, with blood concentrations ranging from ~400 nM in the first 24 h post
271 administration to ~50 nM after 7 days (16, 35, 36). Thus, we tested these
272 concentrations in *P. falciparum* SMFA incubating the drug with the gametocytes
273 before mosquito feeding. Our results of oocyst inhibition with 400 nM pyronaridine 48
274 h incubation suggest the possibility of an impact in transmission in places where
275 Pyramax® was already implemented. These results also support the future design of
276 clinical studies evaluating whether pyronaridine administered in doses higher than
277 180 mg can provide blood concentrations that will have important impact in
278 transmission.

279 In conclusion, the in vitro screens using the *P. berghei* Ookluc line were able to
280 identify compounds active against *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* sexual stages,
281 revealing activity against the first stages of these parasites in the mosquito midgut. In
282 some cases, this activity adds to prior known activities against asexual stages and
283 gametocytes. In other cases, the Ookluc screen revealed antimalarial activity of
284 compounds that are not active against asexual stages. Our list of compounds with

285 transmission blocking potential can thus serve as a guide for future studies for
286 developing antimalarials active against multiple parasite stages.

287

288 **Materials and Methods**

289

290 **Animals and parasite strains.** C57BL/6 or BALB/c mice were bred and
291 maintained in the animal facility of the Department of Parasitology at the Institute of
292 Biomedical Sciences, University of São Paulo, under the protocol 921503119-CEUA
293 of research ethics approval for animal experimentation, or in the NIH animal facility
294 under protocol LMVR 10E. The *P. berghei Ookluc* line was stored as frozen stocks in
295 liquid nitrogen or at -80°C. Vial stocks were prepared by mixing 150 µl of parasitized
296 mouse blood with 300 µl of Alsever's solution (Sigma-Aldrich, A3551) with 10%
297 Glycerol (Sigma-Aldrich, G5516). Mice were infected by intraperitoneal injection of
298 200 µl of thawed stocks. The parasitemia was followed daily through Giemsa staining
299 (Laborclin, 620529 or MilliporeSigma, GS500) of thin blood smears on glass slides
300 (Kasvi, K5-7105-1) counted by direct light microscopy with a 100× oil-immersion
301 objective (Nikon E200).

302

303 **Conversion assays.** For conversion assays, in which gametocytes convert into
304 gametes and fertilize to form zygotes *in vitro*, parasitized mouse blood was obtained
305 by cardiac puncture in heparinized syringes (heparin sodium salt from Sigma-Aldrich,
306 H3393) and added to ookinete medium (1:10 dilution). The ookinete medium (37)
307 consisted of RPMI 1640 (Thermo Scientific, 61870) with 0.025 M HEPES (Thermo
308 Scientific, 15630080), Penicillin-Streptomycin-Neomycin (Sigma-Aldrich, P4083),
309 hypoxanthine 50 mg/L (Sigma-Aldrich, H9636), xanthurenic acid 100 µM (Sigma-
310 Aldrich, D120804), pH = 8.3.

311 For assays in 1536-well plates, the plates were prepared with compound
312 dilutions in 4 µl of ookinete medium in each well. Parasitized blood was first diluted
313 1:1 in PBS at 37°C, then 1 µl of the resulting solution was dispensed in each well with
314 the aid of an automated dispenser (MultiDrop Combi Reagent Dispenser,
315 ThermoFisher Scientific). The plates were kept at 21°C in an incubator for 6 h, and
316 the luciferase activity was determined by measuring Relative Light Units (RLU) using
317 a ViewLux µHTS Microplate Imager (Perkin Elmer) after the addition of one volume
318 of the substrate/lysis buffer (Nano-Glo[®] Luciferase Assay System, Promega). For

319 phenotypic assays, 2 μ l of parasitized blood was added to 20 μ l of ookinete medium
320 in 0.6 ml tubes, the assays were kept at 21°C in an incubator for 1 and 6 h. The
321 luciferase activity was determined by measuring RLU using a microplate reader
322 (POLARstar Omega, BMG LabTech) after the addition of one volume of the
323 substrate/lysis buffer (Nano-Glo[®] Luciferase Assay System, Promega). For some
324 experiments, lysis buffer was not added so the zygotes are not destroyed and can be
325 counted by blood smears made with 2 μ l of the blood cells at the bottom of the tube.
326 Primary screening hits were confirmed through three independent replicates of
327 freshly prepared, serially diluted compounds. For exflagellation assays, 4 μ l of
328 parasitized blood was added to 16 μ l of ookinete medium containing the test
329 compound, incubated at 21°C for 15 min, and the exflagellation centers were counted
330 in twenty 40x fields under light microscopy.

331

332 ***Plasmodium* asexual stage assays.** The *P. falciparum* parasite Dd2 line was
333 cultured *in vitro* using standard conditions (38). Briefly, parasites were maintained in
334 2% human O⁺ erythrocytes (Interstate Blood Bank, Memphis, TN) in RPMI-1640
335 medium (Life Technologies, Grand Island, NY) supplemented with 0.5% Albumax II
336 (Life Technologies), 2 mM l-glutamine, 50 mg/L hypoxanthine, 25 mM HEPES,
337 0.225% NaHCO₃, 24 mM sodium bicarbonate, and 10 μ g/ml gentamycin. Tissue
338 culture flasks and assay plates were incubated at 37 °C under a gas mixture of 5%
339 CO₂, 5% O₂ and 90% N₂. Methods for the SYBR Green-I qHTS (quantitative high-
340 throughput screening), calculation of AC₅₀ (50% of the normalized compound
341 response relative to the maximum response), and definition of curve classes have
342 been described (39-41). qHTS assays were performed using a 11-point
343 concentration-response format, with 72 h of drug exposure. Percent response values
344 represent relative growth as judged by SYBR Green-I fluorescence intensity values
345 normalized to controls.

346

347 **Assay counter screens.** To assess toxicity against mammalian cells, 2×10^3 HepG2
348 cells per well were dispensed into white solid-bottom 1536-well plates in DMEM
349 assay medium using a multidrop combi dispenser in a 5 μ L volume, as described
350 (42). Compounds dissolved in DMSO were transferred to the assay plate via acoustic
351 droplet ejection (Echo 655, Labcyte, San Jose, CA), with a final concentration range
352 of 1.6 nM to 57 μ M. Each plate included media only (no cells) and solvent-only

353 control wells in columns 1–4. The plates were incubated for 48 h at 37 °C, and one
354 volume of CellTiter-Glo assay reagent (Promega, Madison, WI) was added using a
355 BioRAPTR FRD (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA). Cell viability was measured using a
356 ViewLux μ HTS Microplate Imager.

357 To evaluate potential nanoluciferase reporter interference compounds, media
358 from Nluc-expressing S16 cells was filtered through a 0.22 μ m filter (43). Two μ L of
359 Nluc assay substrate (Nano-glo luminescence assay, Promega, Madison, WI) was
360 dispensed per well with a BioRAPTR FRD, compounds were acoustically transferred
361 to the plate with and Echo 655 in concentration-response 11-pt dilutions. After 5 min
362 of substrate and compound incubation at room temperature, 2 μ L of filtered Nluc
363 containing medium was added per well with a BioRAPTR FRD, incubated for 20 min
364 and luminescence was assessed using a ViewLux μ HTS Microplate Imager.

365

366 ***P. falciparum* standard membrane feeding assay.** The standardized methodology
367 for performing the SMFA has been described previously (44). Briefly, 16-18 day old
368 gametocyte cultures of the *P. falciparum* NF54 line (200 μ l of 50% haematocrit
369 culture adjusted to 0.15-0.2% stage V gametocytaemia) were mixed with 60 μ l of a
370 test sample, and the final mixture was immediately fed to ~50 female *Anopheles*
371 *stephensi* (Nijmegen strain, three to six days old) mosquitoes through a membrane-
372 feeding apparatus. Mosquitoes were kept for 8 days and dissected (n=20 per group)
373 to enumerate the oocysts in the midgut. Only midguts from mosquitoes with any eggs
374 at the time of dissection were analyzed (60-80% of mosquitoes were egg positive in
375 general). The human serum and red blood cells used for the gametocyte cultures and
376 feeding experiments were purchased from Interstate Blood Bank.

377

378 ***P. vivax* direct membrane feeding assay.** Patients visiting malaria clinics in north-
379 west Brazil, Rondônia, Porto Velho were microscopically examined for malaria
380 infections. When diagnosed with *P. vivax* infection, \geq 18 years old and not pregnant,
381 they were invited to donate blood for *P. vivax* DMFA. The protocol for blood collection
382 was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Centro de Pesquisa em Medicina
383 Tropical (CEPEM), Rondônia, Brazil (protocol #28176720.9.0000.0011), and written,
384 informed consent was obtained from all volunteers. The blood samples were kept at
385 37°C using a temperature control container during blood transportation and a water
386 bath during blood processing and mosquito feeding. Less than 30 minutes after

387 collection, heparinized blood was aliquoted at 2 mL per tube before being
388 centrifuged, the plasma was removed and a pool of normal human AB⁺ serum (50%
389 hematocrit) was immediately placed in feeding apparatuses and offered to *An.*
390 *darlingi* mosquitoes from a Brazilian colony (45). Two milliliters were offered to 60
391 female mosquitoes. Control groups were fed with infected blood containing DMSO
392 vehicle. Experimental groups were fed with infected blood containing 10, 2 or 0.4 μ M
393 of compound. The mosquitoes were allowed to feed on infected blood for 30 min.
394 After removal of unfed mosquitoes, remaining mosquitoes were kept at the insectary
395 at 26°C \pm 1°C with a relative humidity of 70% \pm 10% and fed daily on a 15% honey
396 solution. Seven days post infection the mosquitoes were dissected, and their midguts
397 were stained with 0.2% commercial mercurochrome and examined for the presence
398 of oocysts to determine the prevalence and infection intensity.

399

400 **Statistical and comparative analysis.** Student's *t*-tests analysis was used to
401 calculate statistical differences between sample groups. The Z-factor for the high-
402 throughput assay was calculated as described (46), with positive controls being wells
403 with conversion assays as described in figure 1b and negative controls being wells
404 with conversion assays with non-parasitized blood or wells with non-activated *Ookluc*
405 (in both cases the RLU signal is the same).

406 For SMFA and DMFA, the best-estimate of % inhibition in oocyst density (%TRA)
407 from multiple feeds, 95% confidence interval of %TRA, and p-value were calculated
408 using a zero-inflated negative binomial model (44).

409

410 **List of Supplementary Materials**

411 Supplementary tables S1 to S9.

412 Supplementary Figure 1.

413

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415

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434

435 **Author contributions**

436

437 Conceptualization: RTE, DYB

438 Methodology: KM, CAL, AS, RTE, DYB

439 Investigation: JC, JEA, BD, XAG

440 Visualization: JC, KM, RTE, DYB

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445

446 **Competing interests**

447

448 The authors declare no competing interests.

449

450 **Data and materials availability**

451

452 All data are available in the main text or the supplementary materials.

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455

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457

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651

652 **Figure legends**

653

654

655 **Figure 1. Illustration of the high-throughput screens with Ookluc.** Three
656 compound collections were used for the primary screen, from which 346 compounds,
657 321 compounds with $IC_{50} < 2 \mu M$, were selected for the validation screens. $IC_{50} < 2$
658 μM was confirmed for 220 compounds, 35 of which had inhibitory activity against
659 nLuc or were toxic to HepG2 cells, remaining 185 compounds with specific inhibitory
660 activity $< 2 \mu M$ against Ookluc fertilization.

661

662

663 **Figure 2. Inhibition of gametocyte activation. (A)** Number of exflagellation centers
664 per 40x field (mean + SD), after 15 min of gametocyte activation in ookinete medium,
665 in the presence of 10 μM of each indicated compound, counted by light microscopy.
666 Results are representative of three independent assays. Bars are mean + SD.
667 Ordinary ANOVA plus Dunnett's test was used for statistics. ***, $p < 0.001$. **(B)**
668 Zygote formation in 6 h conversion assays (mean + SD) in the presence of 10 μM
669 of each indicated compound, measured by relative light units relative to control (%
670 RLU). Results are representative of eight independent assays. Bars are mean + SD.
671 Ordinary ANOVA plus Dunnett's test was used for statistics. ***, $p < 0.001$; *, $p <$
672 0.05.

673

674

675 **Figure 3. Inhibition of zygote formation.** Number of zygotes/ μL counted by light
676 microscopy ($n = 3$) in 1 μL after 1 h **(A)** or 6 h **(B)** of gametocyte activation in
677 ookinete medium in the presence of 10 μM of each indicated compound. Bars are
678 mean + SD. Results are representative of three independent assays. Ordinary
679 ANOVA plus Dunnett's test was used for statistics. ***, $p < 0.001$; *, $p < 0.05$; ns =
680 non-significant.

681

682 **Tables**

683

684 **Table 1. Activity against Ookluc and *P. falciparum* Dd2 asexual stages of the**
685 **seven compounds selected for further characterization.**

686

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)	
	Ookluc	<i>P. falciparum</i> Dd2 asexual stages
DDD107498	0.001	0.014
Fascaplysin	0.022	NA
Pyronaridine	1.399	0.026
Hesperadin	0.437	0.528
Batimastat	0.415	0.011
Quinacrine	1.313	0.167
Nanchangmycin	0.329	0.013

687

688

689 **Table 2. Inhibition of *P. falciparum* oocyst formation by the seven compounds**
 690 **selected for further characterization, added to gametocytes 2 min before *An.***
 691 ***stephensi* feeding.**

692 Note; Each compound at each concentration was tested either in a single assay
 693 (when total mosquito number = 20) or two independent assays (total mosquito
 694 numbers = 40).

695

***P. falciparum* SMFA with compounds added to parasites 2 min before mosquito feeding**

Compound	Drug conc (μ M)	Mosquito Infected/Total	% inhibition of oocyst counts (%TRA)	
			Estimate (95%CI Lo, Hi)	<i>p</i> -value
DDD107498	10	12/40	93.1 (87.3, 96.7)	0.001
	2	23/40	80.1 (65.8, 89.3)	0.001
	0.4	22/40	78.8 (63.5, 88.5)	0.001
Fascaplysin	10	2/40	99.7 (99.0, 99.9)	0.001
	2	25/40	74.0 (54.7, 86.0)	0.001
	0.4	24/40	82.0 (68.6, 90.1)	0.001
Pyronaridine	10	12/40	97.2 (94.6, 98.9)	0.001
	2	20/40	63.1 (36.1, 79.0)	0.001
	0.4	26/40	51.9 (15.1, 71.7)	0.01
Hesperadin	10	0/20	100.0 (99.5, 100.0)	0.001
	2	0/20	100.0 (99.1, 100.0)	0.001
	0.4	0/40	99.9 (99.3, 99.9)	0.001
	0.08	5/20	92.1 (82.1, 97.3)	0.001
	0.016	11/20	43.7 (-22.5, 75.3)	0.147
Batimastat	10	20/20	16.4 (-84.8, 62.0)	0.641
Quinacrine	10	18/20	52.1 (-3.4, 78.8)	0.061
Nanchangmycin	10	0/20	100.0 (99.7, 100.0)	0.001

696

697

698 **Table 3. Inhibition of *P. vivax* oocyst formation by the seven compounds**
 699 **selected for further characterization, added to gametocytes 2 min before *An.***
 700 ***darlingi* feeding.**

701 Note; Each compound at each concentration was tested either in two (when total
 702 mosquito number = 40) or three (total mosquito numbers = 60) independent assays.

703

<i>P. vivax</i> MFA with compounds added to parasites 2 min before mosquito feeding				
Compound	Drug conc (μM)	Mosquito Infected/Total	% inhibition of oocyst counts (%TRA)	
			Estimate (95%CI Lo, Hi)	<i>p</i>-value
DDD107498	10	1/60	99.9 (99.7, 100.0)	0.001
	2	1/40	100.0 (99.8, 100.0)	0.001
	0.4	41/60	86.5 (76.1, 93.1)	0.008
Fascaplysin	10	52/60	-30.0 (-130.2, 23.6)	0.347
Pyronaridine	10	57/60	-17.6 (-102.1, 31.0)	0.583
Hesperadin	10	27/60	99.4 (98.9, 99.7)	0.001
	2	33/60	95.0 (91.3, 97.2)	0.001
	0.4	35/60	77.0 (60.2, 87.7)	0.001
Batimastat	10	58/60	-109.6 (-253.4, -24.1)	0.006
Quinacrine	10	59/60	39.3 (-5.3, 64.7)	0.073
Nanchangmycin	10	0/40	100.0 (99.7, 100.0)	0.001

704

705

706 **Table 4. Inhibition of *P. falciparum* oocyst formation by added to gametocytes**
 707 **24 or 48 h before *An. stephensi* feeding.**
 708

***P. falciparum* SMFA with compounds added to parasites 24/48h before mosquito feeding**

Compound	Time	Drug conc (μ M)	Mosquito Infected/Total	% inhibition of oocyst counts (%TRA)	
				Estimate (95%CI Lo, Hi)	<i>p</i> -value
Pyronaridine	48 h	0.4	15/20	66.7 (27.0, 85.6)	0.005
		0.05	19/20	10.7 (-112.1, 63.5)	0.821
	24 h	0.4	15/20	50.5 (-14.0, 78.2)	0.097
		0.05	20/20	-37.2 (-213.6, 37.7)	0.459

709

Primary Screens

A

B

